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Using Virtual Reality Technology to Study Physics

Dilshodov Abrorjon Dilshodjon oqli.

Fergana branch of Tashkent University of Information Technology named after Muhammad al-Khwarazmi, Uzbekistan.

Abstract: *With the development of information technology, other industries are also developing, and completely different, previously unfamiliar ways of communicating, creating, and learning something become popular. Thus, the modern world places increasingly new demands on the learning process. However, despite the development of distance and inclusive education, natural sciences, due to their characteristics, lag behind others in the application of new technologies. This is due to the fact that in order to effectively acquire skills in working with equipment and the ability to analyze experimental data, physics, chemistry and other exact disciplines require laboratory work. However, this requires specially equipped laboratories, which are not always equipped in educational institutions. Then new technologies come to the rescue, such as computer graphics, augmented reality, computational dynamics, etc.*

This article discusses the use of modern technologies in the field of education. An analysis was made of the implementation of various innovative developments based on virtual reality in some areas of modern life. The paper presents the advantages and possibilities of using educational resources based on virtual reality in education and, in particular, for the study of physics. The authors presented their own software product that allows you to study physics using virtual reality. This approach made interaction with the application more interesting and memorable, and learning more effective. The cross-platform environment Unity 3D was chosen as the development platform. The main functionality was written in C#. Graphic models were created using Substance Painter. The article discusses the development process of the presented application, its functionality, as well as the user interface.

The work done allowed the authors to determine the advantages of using new technologies in the study of physics and showed that they open up new prospects for their widespread use at different stages of education in educational institutions of various levels. This approach, in addition to the above advantages, makes the learning process safe, interesting and more accessible. As a result, not only software was obtained, but also new experience that will be used for further development and research.

Keywords: *Virtual reality, unity 3D, leap motion, virtual physical laboratory, physics.*

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of new information technologies, along with the computerization of educational institutions and the innovative activities of the teaching staff of higher educational institutions, are the main directions of the comprehensive modernization of education, which receive special attention not only throughout the world. An example of this is the “Digital Kazakhstan” development program developed by the government of the republic. One of the goals of this program is to increase the digital literacy of the population, including in secondary, technical and vocational, as well as higher education, training and retraining of personnel. Today we can observe a global trend - Industry 4.0 - for the mass introduction of cyber-physical systems, such as artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, quantum computing, 3D printing, as well as autonomous robots in production and everyday life, including education. Information technology also has a huge impact on this area, not only from the computerization of all business processes of higher and secondary educational institutions, as well as from any organizations, but also from the introduction of new methods and teaching aids based on modern technologies. In the latter direction, computer training systems occupy a prominent place, for example, such as virtual laboratories, which allow experiments to be carried out in the complete absence of a real installation, in which all processes are simulated using a computer.

Review of Literature

Currently, students' perception of the material being studied can be improved with the help of new visualization elements and gestures that modern digital technologies offer. In particular, with virtual reality technology (VR – Virtual Reality), new ways of teaching come to the fore, which make it possible to reveal the student’s interest in the subject being studied, stimulate positive emotions, speed up the learning process and help better assimilation. VR introduces an element of play into the learning process, which certainly has a positive effect on students’ results.

Thus, the analysis of the virtual environment used for students to study issues of tourism development and related impacts is considered. Virtual reality is used to fully immerse students in the environment. This approach can provide participants with a holistic experience of the real environment, which in reality is expensive, especially for groups with large numbers of participants. The pedagogical value of such experiences is achieved through immersion in a reality-based environment, interaction with complex and ambiguous situations and information, and interaction with the space, other students and teachers. The results demonstrate that developing such complex virtual learning environments is possible, but the main challenge is achieving high levels of interactivity.

Learning and teaching algebra concepts often presents challenges, both for students in terms of understanding and for teachers in terms of presentation of the material. An example of a course is provided in which the study of algebra is offered using virtual reality technology. The authors have developed an open educational resource, Virtual Algebra Tiles, which allows students to expand their knowledge of

algebra concepts using a computer. The results showed that such a learning system is more comfortable for students, transforming the learning process into an enjoyable task.

A study was conducted on how gifted students perceive virtual programs. Students were enrolled in a virtual course. Data were collected through asynchronous focus groups on an online discussion board, observations of synchronous activities in their virtual classroom, and individual interviews with participants. Research has shown that some technical difficulties occurred, mainly due to operator errors or failure to use available tools. In terms of curriculum and pedagogy, participants saw little difference between traditional and virtual classrooms. It can be concluded that for gifted students, the quality of content and instruction exceeds the reality of the learning environments. This information can be used in the future to improve the quality of on-line education or to create new educational resources.

This paper examines faculty perceptions regarding the integration of virtual reality into teaching through a case study in an information technology (IT) department at a university in the Middle East. The respondents interviewed in this study consisted of faculty members. A quantitative method was used: an adapted questionnaire was distributed among IT teachers on the Internet, which assessed their opinion on the possibility of using virtual reality as a teaching tool. Statistical methods were used to analyze the questionnaire data. The results obtained from quantitative data revealed teachers' willingness to use VR systems as an additional teaching tool, their intention to include them in the teaching process in the future, barriers to technology use, and users' prior knowledge of technology. The results also showed that training can be most effective with the integration of VR technology. The article also provides recommendations to facilitate the use of VR technology as a teaching tool.

A purpose-designed and tested virtual reality learning environment can offer medical students a means of accessing and reviewing learning materials, thereby improving learning outcomes. In addition, the use of such learning tools makes medical education more accessible. The article also shows that virtual reality (VR) has unique potential to transform medical education and offers increased investment in the development of such technologies and the opportunity to collaborate with developers.

It examines the use of virtual reality technology to obtain evacuation information, which is key to reducing injuries and increasing survival rates. Serious games (SGs) based on immersive virtual reality represent an innovative approach to learning and educating people in a gaming environment. This paper aims to understand the development and implementation of such serious games in the context of training and research in building evacuation applied to various indoor emergency situations such as fire and earthquake. The study examined the effectiveness of using immersive virtual reality to study the effects of climate change, in particular to study the acidity of seawater. Research has shown that after experiencing immersive virtual reality, people demonstrated a good level of knowledge, curiosity about climate science, and in some cases showed greater environmental awareness. The analysis also showed that immersive virtual reality was a promising complementary mechanism for effective learning, as the more people explored the spatial learning environment, the higher the level of knowledge about environmental change they demonstrated. Additionally, learning gains have been shown across a variety of conditions: participant level (high school, college students, adults), degree (learning outcomes, virtual

world motion data tracking, qualitative responses), and content (multiple versions of changes were tested climate). Thus, immersive virtual environments are an effective tool for studying climate change.

The use of virtual reality technology for the study of architecture is considered. Due to its experiential nature, VR technology can be very effective for architectural education. The authors have developed an app called LADUVR that users can use on a construction site to take a closer look at architectural details and test what they've learned in an interactive and immersive environment. The article also provides a comparison between traditional teaching methods and the use of virtual reality technology.

The use of innovative technologies in museum activities, such as virtual reality technology, is relevant because this technology makes it possible to present information in a more visual, interesting and memorable form, resulting in the opportunity to attract more visitors. It offers guidelines for developing educational games in collaboration with a museum. That mini educational games using virtual reality technology greatly help students in learning artistic concepts.

This article presents an educational resource implemented in the form of an application with a set of practical tasks for studying physics using virtual reality technology.

Development of a virtual physics laboratory

The International University of Information Technologies has experience in using information technologies in the educational process. For example, in the Physics discipline, laboratory work is performed virtually using an application developed by the authors. Simulation of physical experiments is carried out in a virtual environment. Students have the opportunity to set initial parameters and observe the physical process as many times as they wish.

The project presented in this article is related to the use of virtual reality in the process of studying physics. The authors created an application with a set of practical tasks in physics using VR. The developed application provides access to physical problems in such sections as kinematics, fundamentals of dynamics, elements of statics, conservation laws in mechanics, mechanical vibrations and waves, molecular physics and thermodynamics.

One of the distinctive features of the proposed application is its multilingualism. The user is given the opportunity to choose Kazakh, Russian or English language for interaction with the application. Therefore, this educational resource can be used abroad.

In this project, the cross-platform computer game development environment, the Unity 3D game engine from Unity Technologies, was used for software development. The app works with a wired Leap motion sensor designed for handheld tracking in virtual reality.

The presented virtual laboratory application using Leap motion consists of the components shown in Figure 1. The structure consists of the Main Launcher, which opens the application and calls the following two modules: tasks in the sections “Mechanics”, “Electrostatics”, etc. and tasks with support Leap motion controller. The user sees only the graphical interface, but three more components are hidden behind it: a general folder containing models, scripts and other necessary resources, separate folders for a specific task, and a folder necessary for Leap motion to work correctly.

The user's interaction with the application is described in Figure 2. Here are the possible actions performed by the user. For example, the user must connect the Leap motion controller at the beginning of work. Only after this the full functionality of the application becomes available to him. In it, he can select a problem, view the condition, solution, turn on the demonstration, and also change its parameters. All this happens thanks to the menu Controller, since it is with the help of it that the user interacts with the application.

Figure 3 shows the main menu of the application with the Leap motion controller integrated into it.

Figure 1 – Diagram of application components with Leap motion

Figure 2 – Use case diagram

Each problem contains a condition, an animated problem scene, and a solution. Let's consider an example of implementing a problem with a pendulum. The condition of the problem is as follows: will the period of oscillation of a mathematical pendulum change if it is placed in water? The pendulum is given a perfectly streamlined shape, so that friction with water can be neglected. A demonstration of the experiment is shown in Figure 4 (a, b).

Figure 3 – Main menu of the application with Leap motion

a) b)
Figure 4 – Example of a task with Leap motion

Interactive control is organized using a Leap motion controller, keyboard and camera view (mouse control), which also allows you to rotate 3D scenes in different directions. In addition, the program allows you to enlarge the objects under study for a more detailed overview. When positions and viewpoints change, the dialog box updates. Interactivity in this work is the main advantage, ensuring clarity and quick assimilation of the material being studied.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The development of the presented virtual complex was made possible thanks to the development of modern information technologies. Their current level makes it possible to implement a wide variety of projects, which opens up new horizons for creating training resources and tools at a qualitatively different level. With the development of technology, society also develops, which, in turn, requires the use of new approaches to learning. Thus, the use of the latest technical means helps to create completely different educational programs, original in their structure, that are interesting to the current generation of students and students of other educational institutions. We believe that the virtual laboratory we created for the discipline “Physics” is a program that meets the requirements of our time and is effective in the study of this subject. Currently, the authors are constantly working to develop new practical tasks and their integration into the laboratory.

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